

MARKS OF CHRISTIAN FELLOWSHIP (PHILIPPIANS 2:1-4)

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In this exegesis paper, I would like to provide the exegesis of Philippians 2:1-4. I would like to provide the exegesis in the following order: thesis statement and methodology, outline of the content, introduction, Greek text of the passage, English translation, historical and literal context, the interpretation of the text, conclusion and application, and bibliography.¹

Thesis Statement and Methodology

The thesis of this passage is Christian fellowship should be marked by unity, humility, and thoughtful service. In this paper, I would like to demonstrate my proposition with the help of translation, historical and literary context, careful exegesis of the passage with word study and theological insights, and conclusions. In this paper, I did not attempt to provide an exhaustive commentary. Instead, the paper is designed to explain the main thesis of the passage.

Content Outline

1. The Foundation for Unity and Service: Christian Fellowship (2:1)
 - A. Encouragement in Christ (2:1a)
 - B. Comfort in Love (2:1b)
 - C. Fellowship in the Spirit (2:1c)
 - D. Affection and Sympathy (2:1d)
2. The Motivation for Unity and Service: Complete the Joy of the Apostle (2:2a)

¹J. Scott Duvall and J. Daniel Hays, *Grasping God's Word: A Hands-On Approach to Reading, Interpreting, and Applying the Bible*. 2nd ed. Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2005. 421-422. I adopted the exegesis paper format of Duvall and Hays with few modifications.

3. The Pathway to Unity and Service: Right Attitude and Disposition (2:2b-2:4)

A. Call for Unity (2:2b-2e)

- i. Have the Same Opinion (2:2b)
- ii. Have the Same Love (2:2c)
- iii. Be in Harmony (2:2d)
- iv. Think One Thing (2:2e)

B. Call for Selfless Humility (2:3)

- i. Do Nothing according to Selfish Ambition and Vain Glory (2:3a)
- ii. Prefer Others more than Yourselves in Humility (2:3b)

C. Call for Thoughtfulness (2:4)

- i. Do not Look for Your Own Interests (2:4a)
- ii. Look for the Interests of Others (2:4b).

Introduction

The church of Jesus Christ always struggled with theological conflicts, false-teachings, political upheavals, personal conflicts within the church, and persecution etc.,. Such problems naturally damage the unity of the church. How should the church respond in those situations? Did God give us any guidelines to tackle such issues? What are some necessary attitudes and dispositions to keep the unity and integrity of the church? The apostle Paul gave us some instructions to keep the unity of the church in the midst of theological disputes, political impulsiveness, personal conflicts, and problematic leadership. Paul exhorted the Christians to be united in fellowship, disposition, and humble service. He warned the church members to avoid selfish ambition and conceit. He instructed the church to pursue humility and humble service.

Greek Text: Philippians 2:1-4

2 1Εἴ τις οὖν παράκλησις ἐν Χριστῷ, εἴ τι παραμύθιον ἀγάπης, εἴ τις κοινωνία πνεύματος, εἴ τις σπλάγγνα καὶ οἰκτιρμοί, 2πληρώσατέ μου τὴν χαρὰν ἵνα τὸ αὐτὸ φρονῆτε, τὴν αὐτὴν ἀγάπην ἔχοντες, σύμψυχοι, τὸ ἐν φρονοῦντες, 3μηδὲν κατ' ἐριθείαν μηδὲ κατὰ κενοδοξίαν ἀλλὰ τῇ ταπεινοφροσύνῃ ἀλλήλους ἠγούμενοι ὑπερέχοντας ἑαυτῶν, 4μὴ τὰ ἑαυτῶν ἕκαστος σκοποῦντες ἀλλὰ [καὶ] τὰ ἐτέρων ἕκαστοι.²

English Translation: Philippians 2:1-4

2 1Therefore, if there is any exhortation in Christ, if there is any comfort from love, if there is any fellowship in the Spirit, if there is any affection and mercy, 2(then) complete my joy, by having the same opinion, by having the same love, by being harmonious, by thinking one (thing), 3by doing nothing according to selfish ambition, (and) not according to the vain glory, but in humility preferring others more than yourselves, 4by each one not look for his own interests, but also the interests of others.³

Historical and Literary Context

Historical Context

Apostle Paul founded the church in Philippi during his second missionary journey (Acts 16:6-40).⁴ He had good relationship with the church at Philippi. He was also receiving financial support from the church. Some of the challenges at the church of Philippi include the

² Novum Testamentum Graece (NA 28), [academic-bible.com](https://www.academic-bible.com), <https://www.academic-bible.com/en/online-bibles/novum-testamentum-graece-na-28/> This online edition of the Greek New Testament is based on the Novum Testamentum Graece (Nestle-Aland), 28. Edition, @ Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, Stuttgart 2012.

³ The translation is provided to help the flow of thought. The passage is translated with the help of the resources mentioned in bibliography.

⁴ Andreas J Köstenberger, L. Scott Kellum, and Charles L Quarles. *The Cradle, the Cross, and the Crown: An Introduction to the New Testament* (version 2nd ed.). 2nd ed. Nashville, TN: B & H Publishing Group, 2016, 645.

presence of false teachers, some problematic people who preach the gospel with selfish motives, and disunity in the church. The church struggled with pride, strife, and disunity in some form. Paul wrote a letter to address the issues in the church, to promote Christ-centered unity, and to encourage the church. He wrote this letter from the roman imprisonment in approximately AD 59 (Phil 1:13; 4:22). He was also planning to send Timothy and Epaphroditus to the church at Philippi. He also expressed his desire to visit them after his release from the prison.⁵

Literary Context

The epistle to the Philippians is considered as a “letter of friendship.” In terms of rhetoric, the letter contains epideictic and deliberative material.⁶ The epistle contains a greeting (1:1-2), thanksgiving and prayer (1:3-11), exhortations to unity and humility with examples (1:12-2:30), warnings against false teachers and internal disunity (3:1-4:9), appreciation for the support (4:10-20), and final greetings (4:21-23).⁷ In chapter 1, 1:1-2, Paul greeted the church along with his coworker Timothy. In 1:3-11, he gave thanks and prayed for them. He longed for them, and he desired that they grow in their love, and they will be filled with the fruit of righteousness. In 1:12-18, he explained how his imprisonment advanced the gospel. He also mentioned his suffering with people who preach the gospel with selfish motives. In 1:19-26, Paul assured the believers in Philippi to have confidence in God that Christ will be honored in his body, either through his death or his life. He encouraged them to delight in the possible good news of his deliverance. He was hoping that he would be seen by the church at Philippi. In 1:27-30, Paul exhorted Christians to live a faithful life in accordance with the gospel. He exhorted them to continue firmly in their faith in the midst of affliction. He also needed them to

⁵ Köstenberger, Kellum, and Quarles, 638-639.

⁶ Köstenberger, Kellum, and Quarles, 646-647.

⁷ Köstenberger, Kellum, and Quarles, 648.

be united in the midst of conflict. In chapter 2, 2:5-18, he exhorted the believers to grow in Christlike humility. He exhorted them to pursue the faith with earnestness. He required them to be above reproach.⁸

The church at Philippi suffered challenges with three groups of people who threatened the advancement of the gospel. The first group were the preachers who proclaim the gospel with selfish ambitions. They were envious of Paul's work. The gospel was advanced despite the challenge of these preachers (1:12-26). The second group were the false teachers. They put their confidence in the flesh (Jewish ethnicity), and they mandated circumcision for believers. Paul vehemently opposed their false teaching, and he called out their selfish motives (3:1-16). The third group were the believers who fight with each other and bring division into the church (1:27-2:1-11; 4:2-3). Paul addressed their selfish attitudes and prescribed humility to restore their fellowship.⁹

Content: Interpretation of the Text

If Christians want to enjoy the fellowship of the gospel, they should obey the implication of the gospel. Paul knew that the church at Philippi suffered persecution, afflictions, false teachers, and internal divisions. Despite those challenges, they still enjoyed the privileges from Christian fellowship. They enjoyed companionship, encouragement, comfort, love, and affection. Some members in the church focused to live for their own benefits. They enjoyed their privileges. They did not care for others. Now, Paul contended that they cannot exploit their privileges for their own advantage. Instead, they should pursue unity, love, harmony, and service with humility and servant heart.

⁸ Köstenberger, Kellum, and Quarles, 648-651.

⁹ Walter A Elwell, and Robert W Yarbrough. *Encountering the New Testament: A Historical and Theological Survey*. 2nd ed. Encountering Biblical Studies. Grand Rapids, Mich.: Baker Academic, 2005, 314-315.

Foundation for Unity and Service: Christian Fellowship (2:1)

Paul used the inferential conjugation οὖν to refer to his previous statement in 1:27-30.

The current exhortation in 2:1-4 is based on the previous exhortation in 1:27-30.¹⁰ In 1:27-30, Paul exhorted Christians to live a faithful life in accordance with the gospel. They should be united in response to the external attacks. He exhorted them to stand firm and united in the midst of affliction. Now, Paul is continuing the same thought. But in 2:1-4, he focused his attention to the internal attitudes, and he exhorted the church to be united in love, humility, and service.

Encouragement in Christ - Παράκλησις ἐν Χριστῷ (2:1a)

Paul used four first class conditionals εἰ to exhort the church. Paul did not doubt the presence of exhortation, comfort, fellowship, and compassion in the church. The meaning of the phrases should be understood as “assumed to be true.”¹¹ He knew that they had those privileges in the church. Those very privileges became premises for his exhortations to the church. Since the church experience God’s exhortation, comfort, fellowship, and compassion, they should express them to others, especially to the members within the church.

All four phrases (παράκλησις ἐν Χριστῷ, παραμύθιον ἀγάπης, κοινωνία πνεύματος, σπλάγχνα καὶ οἰκτιρμοί) in verse 1 refers to the same idea of privilege of fellowship. However, each phrase and word carry the weight of Paul’s argument. Although the word παράκλησις has three possible meanings (exhortation, strong appeal, and comfort), in this context Paul is

¹⁰ Reumann, John, *Philippians: A New Translation with Introduction and Commentary*. The Anchor Yale Bible, V. 33b. New Haven: Yale University Press, 2008, 298.

¹¹ Reumann, *Philippians*, 298.

referring to the exhortation in Christ.¹² The exhortations that people of God enjoy are part of common life in Christ (ἐν Χριστῷ).¹³

Comfort in Love - Παραμύθιον Αγάπης (2:1b)

The meaning of the word παραμύθιον is encouragement, comfort or consolation. This comfort refers to the encouragement given to a depressed person or group.¹⁴ The church at Philippi suffered persecution and disunity. However, they still had comfort from God and people. The source of their comfort is from the love (ἀγάπης). This love refers to the love in a Christian fellowship. It comes from God, one another in the fellowship, and/or apostle Paul and his coworkers. Since Paul did not specify the source of the love, it is safe to assume that the church enjoyed the love from all three sources: triune God, Christian community, and apostles and ministers.¹⁵

Fellowship in the Spirit - Κοινωνία Πνεύματος (2:1c)

The meaning of the word κοινωνία is fellowship. It involves a close association, sharing, communion, and close relationship.¹⁶ The church at Philippi enjoyed this fellowship in the Spirit (πνεύματος). The church enjoyed fellowship and partnership within the community. The church enjoyed the presence and participation of the Spirit.¹⁷ The church supposed to share

¹² Walter Bauer, and William F Arndt., *A Greek-English Lexicon of the New Testament and Other Early Christian Literature* (BDAG), Edited by Frederick W Danker. Third ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2000, 825.

¹³ Reumann, *Philippians*, 299.

¹⁴ BDAG, 828.

¹⁵ Reumann, *Philippians*, 301-302.

¹⁶ BDAG, 618.

¹⁷ Reumann, *Philippians*, 302-303.

their life with one another, participate in the work and fellowship of the Spirit, and need to be empowered by the very same Spirit.

Affection and Sympathy - Σπλάγχνα καὶ Οἰκτιρμοί (2:1d)

Paul used hendiadys with two closely associated words *σπλάγχνα καὶ οἰκτιρμοί* to refer to affection and compassion in the church. The word *σπλάγχνα* is a general term and *οἰκτιρμοί* is a specific term.¹⁸ The meaning of the word *σπλάγχνα* is affection or love.¹⁹ It refers to the love and affection within the church. The inflected word *σπλάγχνα* is a nominative neuter plural of the root *σπλάγγνον*. The meaning of the word *οἰκτιρμοί* is mercy, compassion, and pity. It is the display of concern over another's misfortune.²⁰ The inflected word *οἰκτιρμοί* is a nominative masculine plural form of root word *οἰκτιρμός*. The other similar meanings include warmth affection, compassion, and tenderness.²¹ The church is enjoying the affection and mercy from one another in the community and from God.²²

In verse 1, Paul's main contention is if the members of the church enjoy the privileges of Christian community including exhortation, comfort, fellowship, affection, and mercy, then the church should also learn to manifest their love by pursuing unity, humility, and thoughtfulness.

Motivation for Unity and Service: Complete the Joy of the Apostle (2:2a)

Paul previously expressed his joy over the church at Philippi (Phil 1:3-4). The church participated in the work of the gospel. The church demonstrated their love and affection. He had

¹⁸ Reumann, *Philippians*, 302-303.

¹⁹ BDAG, 994.

²⁰ BDAG, 762.

²¹ Reumann, *Philippians*, 303.

²² Reumann, *Philippians*, 304.

the joy on the account of Philippians. However, his joy needs to be completed. The church still needed to grow in love, knowledge, unity, humility, and service etc., (Phil 1:4-11). Πληρώσατέ is aorist active imperative form of πληρόω. It introduces the apodosis for previous first-class conditionals in verse 1. This imperative also sets the imperatival tone for the rest of the passage (Phil 2:2-4).²³ Now, Paul called the church to fulfill his joy by pursuing unity and service.

Pathway for Unity and Service: Right Attitude and Dispositions (2:2b-2:4)

The members in the church should develop right attitudes and dispositions to serve one another, advance the gospel, to bring joy to the apostle, and to glorify God. These right attitudes and dispositions should not be considered as alien concepts. Christ himself expressed his unity of mind with father in fulfilling God's plan, demonstrated his humility, obedience, and thoughtfulness toward others in his incarnation, service, and crucifixion.

Call for Unity (2:2b-2e)

The particle ἵνα introduces the content clause. It is an expegetical substantival clause. It explains how the Philippians could complete Paul's joy.²⁴ The right attitude for pursuing unity is by thinking in harmony, having the same love, being in full accord, and by thinking in a united way.

Have the Same Opinion - Τὸ Αὐτὸ Φρονῆτε (2:2b)

The parsing of the word φρονῆτε is present active subjunctive of φρονέω. The meaning of the word φρονέω is to have an opinion or to judge something.²⁵ The church at Philip

²³ William C. Varner, *Philippians: A Linguistic Commentary*. Santa Clarita, CA, 2017, 55

²⁴ Varner, *Philippians*, 55.

²⁵ BDAG, 1121.

was called to think in the same way about different issues.²⁶ They should be united in their thinking. When the church suffers any external or internal threats, the church should start think with a single mind. Since they have the same foundation and participation, they should react to the threats as a single body.

**Have the Same Love - Τὴν αὐτὴν Αγάπην
ἔχοντες (2:2c)**

The church should have the same equal love towards one another. Church received love from God. The church is enjoying the love and fellowship of one another and the love of the ministers. Now, the church members should express their love in a similar way.²⁷

Be in Harmony - Σύμψυχοι (2:2d)

The church should be harmonious and in one accord. They should be united in one spirit. They should join together as one living unity.^{28,29} The church should thrive as one living unity. When the church suffers different attacks, they should respond with one accord and in unity.

**Think One Thing - Τὸ ἓν Φρονοῦντες
(2:2e)**

The church should have one and the same thinking. The church should not be divided by different opinions. Perhaps, Paul reiterated the same truth. He reminded the church to fulfill

²⁶ Reumann, *Philippians*, 305.

²⁷ Reumann, *Philippians*, 305.

²⁸ Reumann, *Philippians*, 306.

²⁹ Varner, *Philippians*, 56.

one goal—fulfill his joy³⁰ by pursuing unity and service. In verses 2:3-11, Paul reminded the church to serve one another with humility.

Call for Selfless Humility (2:3)

After exhorting the church to seek unity, he pointed out the need for selfless service and humility.

Do Nothing according to Selfish Ambition and Vain Glory - μηδὲν κατ' ἐριθείαν μηδὲ κατὰ κενοδοξίαν (2:3a)

Paul exhorted the church to forsake selfish ambition and vain glory. This is necessary for unity and service. The meaning of the word ἐριθείαν is selfishness, selfish ambition, strife, and contentiousness.³¹ Christians should not live a self-seeking life. They should not seek their own advantage.³² The meaning of the word κενοδοξίαν is conceit, excessive ambition, vanity, and exaggerated self-evaluation.³³ The church at Philippi suffered such self-seeking preachers and false teachers (Phil 3:2-4). The attitude of selfishness and conceit produces quarrels and divisions in the church (Phil 2:14-16, Titus 3:9-11, 2 Tim 2:23-24). Christians should not pursue fellowship with self-seeking motives and conceit. Such attitude brings calamity to the church.³⁴

³⁰ Reumann, *Philippians*, 306.

³¹ BDAG, 459.

³² Reumann, *Philippians*, 307.

³³ BDAG, 604.

³⁴ Ralph P Martin, *Philippians: An Introduction and Commentary*. Tyndale New Testament Commentaries, Volume 11. England: InterVarsity Press, 1987, 93.

Prefer Others More Than Yourself in Humility - τῇ ταπεινοφροσύνῃ ἀλλήλους ἡγούμενοι ὑπερέχοντας ἑαυτῶν (2:3b)

Instead of seeking glory with selfish ambition and conceit, the church should pursue humility and concern for others. The church members should value others more significant than themselves. When church deals with various issues, they should consider, regard, and think about others. The church members should honor one another within the church (Rom 12:10).³⁵

Call for Thoughtfulness (2:4)

The church members should be thoughtful in serving one another. The church cannot attain unity and maturity if they seek their own interests.

Not Looking for Your Own Interests - μὴ τὰ ἑαυτῶν ἕκαστος σκοποῦντες. (2:4a)

Paul exhorted the church members to avoid the temptation to seek self-interests. A member of the Christian community should not always be concerned of one own's personal interests. If the Christians are preoccupied with their own achievements, interests, and advantages, they fail to serve to others.³⁶

Look for the Interests of Others - τὰ ἑτέρων ἕκαστοι (2:4b).

Christians should value and appreciate the gifts, achievements, and good qualities in other members in the church. They need to look for the interests of others. They should find ways to serve other members in the church. They need to look to Jesus Christ who became man,

³⁵ Reumann, *Philippians*, 308.

³⁶ Martin, *Philippians*, 94.

gave himself and died on the cross for the service of others (2:5-11). They need to imitate the model of apostles and ministers of the gospel (2:19-30).³⁷

Conclusion and Application

First, Christians should pursue loving fellowship in their local churches with a bond of unity and love. Christians should strive to exhort and comfort and to show affection and kindness to one another. Second, Christians should avoid the temptation to fulfill selfish ambitions. They should avoid envy and conceit. If we work with selfish ambitions or conceit in the church, we will spoil God's work. This is not acceptable for heavenly citizens and members of the new covenant community. Instead, Christians should see one another as members of a same family and seek to serve one another. Third, Christians should serve one another with Christ-like humility. Christ is the Son of God, the second person of the trinity. However, he did not take advantage of his sonship and divine prerogatives. Instead, he became a man in his incarnation. He did not indulge himself in the worldly pleasures. He fulfilled God's will and served his people. He served God the father with humility, obedience, and servant heart. He served people. He healed their sicknesses, he preached the gospel to them, and he mentored the disciples. He glorified God through his obedience and faithful service. Jesus also reminded his disciples that he himself came to serve people (Matthew 20:28). Therefore, they should have an attitude of servant to serve others (Matthew 23:11). Christians should imitate Christ in his humility and sacrificial love. Therefore, Christian fellowship should be marked by unity, humility, and thoughtful service.

³⁷ Martin, *Philippians*, 94-95.

The main idea of this passage is_ Christian fellowship should be marked by unity in thinking, love, conformity, and planning, lack of selfish ambition and conceit, and evidence of humility and thoughtfulness towards others (servant heart).

Christians should seek the fellowship by pursuing unity, love, harmony, and service in the church. They should serve one another with Christ-like humility and thoughtfulness toward others. Christians should make use of the opportunities of fellowship to pursue unity, love, harmony, and service in the church. They should serve one another with Christ-like humility and thoughtfulness toward others. The main idea of this passage is_ the obedience to the gospel of Jesus Christ demands unity, love, harmony, lack of selfish ambition, and Christ-like humility and service in the church. The main idea is Paul's joy is dependent on the unity and loving fellowship of Christians. If they don't have love and brotherly love, then there is no joy and no glory. If all they do is fighting, arguing, and grumbling, they will bring disrepute on the gospel. Paul will not be happy if they have disunity and good faith. In fact, the unity and brotherly love are the markers of Christian love. Christians should maintain brotherly love and unity especially in the times of suffering and persecution. The members in the church should make the most of the Christian fellowship and develop unity of mind, selfless humility, and thoughtfulness to serve one another in the church. This will be accomplished only when they have same mind in their daily activities, when they are encouraging one another, comforting one another. This can be achieved only if they don't do anything from rivalry and conceit, instead they need to count others more significant than themselves in humility, they should not look for their own interests, but they also need to look for the interests of others. Paul knows that Philippians have comfort, consolation, participation in the Spirit etc., but the problem is they do not have unity, same mind,

same accord etc., That's why Paul exhorts them to have same mind. Otherwise, it will not bring joy to him. In a sense, Paul's joy is contingent upon the unity of the church at Philippi.

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